

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN CLINICAL, NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL AND HEMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH FIRST OPEN OVERALL GLAUCOMA IN PATIENTS WITH HYPERTONIC DEAD

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Annotation. Normal tension glaucoma is a form of multifactorial optical neuropathy, the etiology of which is still actively debated. To date, no single factor can fully explain its pathogenesis. The main factors contributing to glaucomatous optical neuropathy (ON) associated with GNN include vascular factors and ocular blood flow, translaminar pressure gradient as well as immune and genetic factors. These factors can ocular blood flow cause axonal damage in several ways.

Keywords: glaucoma, optic disc excavation, intraocular pressure

Materials and Methods. 90 patients with primary open angle glaucoma combined with hypertension were examined. Systemic hemodynamics of the patients with estimation of coefficient of variability of systolic and diastolic blood pressure as well as cerebral hemodynamics with estimation of vasomotor reactivity during stress test and parameters of ocular hemodynamics in POAG patients with various levels of BP in the dynamics of the disease have been studied.

Results: Standard automated perimetry results were reduced. Those patients who had previously used antiglaucoma drops were advised to discontinue them for up to 3 weeks (drug washout period), the remaining patients had newly detected glaucoma. As inclusion criteria, emmetropic refraction and open AAC were considered, confirmed by anterior segment optical coherence tomography, with an anterior chamber angle of at least 30° being acceptable. Only patients without previous eye surgery were included in the analysis. Our goal was to achieve an individually set target pressure at which no glaucoma progression is expected and at which the absence of progression can be observed and documented. In each patient, the target pressure is determined based on the existing glaucomatous lesion, current intraocular pressure, rate of structural and functional progression, other risk factors present and potential side-effects of treatment. These considerations determine the initial treatment interventions. Percentage pressure reduction rate is no longer recommended as the sole

treatment target, as it does not take into account the absolute level of initial intraocular pressure, which is an important component. Typical target pressures are < 21 mmHg for early glaucoma, < 18 mmHg for moderate glaucoma and < 15 mmHg for advanced glaucoma. Whichever target is set, the further progression of intraocular pressure should be regularly checked to determine whether the disease has stabilised as desired or has progressed further, in which case the target pressure may need to be revised.

Conclusions: Prostaglandin analogues are usually prescribed for initial treatment and are used once a day, in the evening. These drugs improve uveoscleral and trabecular outflow and thereby reduce intraocular pressure. Their side effects include conjunctival hyperemia, increased eyelash growth, decreased periorbital fat and increased pigmentation of the iris and periocular skin. Systemic conditions limiting the use of prostaglandin analogues include bronchial asthma, severe cardiovascular disease and liver or kidney disease.

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